

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF FORMATION OF PROFESSION-ORIENTED COMMUNICATION COMPETENCES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The author provides information on ways to develop communicative competence as part of the implementation of new educational standards for higher professional education. The article presents the results on the formation of communicative competence, including work on the formation of homogeneous groups, language competence, the introduction of the communicative method and project work.*

Keywords: *communication, project work, English language, competence development, professional education.*

INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of the competency-based approach, specialists in the field of foreign languages consider various competencies, including such as subject, communicative, activity, developmental; But communicative competence is always highlighted as the main one, since it is this competence that is the basis for the development of all other competencies. The concept of “communicative competence” comes from the Latin word “competere” (to achieve, to comply). Communicative competence means the ability to solve communication problems relevant to students from everyday, educational, industrial and cultural life, the ability to use the facts of language and speech to achieve communication goals. This is a person’s ability to realize linguistic competence in various conditions of speech communication [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

General cultural competencies include the following [2]:

- knowledge of world culture and the willingness to rely on them in one’s personal and general cultural development;
- knowledge and understanding of the laws of development of nature, society and thinking and the ability to operate with this knowledge in professional activities;
- ability to take an active civic position;
- ability to analyze and evaluate historical events and processes, etc.

The principles underlying this experiment are as follows:

- introduction of the principle of creating “homogeneous” (homogeneous) groups;
- introduction of communicative methods of teaching English;
- teaching business English, starting from the 1st year;
- the use of project work in the process of teaching English.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since students in a homogeneous group have approximately the same level of training and development, an atmosphere of emancipation, mutual understanding, real communication and confidence in their knowledge is formed in the group [1], which leads to a high level of assimilation of the studied material and, consequently, the formation of communicative competencies.

When introducing the communicative method, we focus on the following characteristics of this method, considering them the most important:

- the teacher invites students to use language in communication situations;
- language is presented according to function rather than form;
- the student learns to use language adequately in a certain social context;
- the student learns to “take risks” in using the language, while mistakes are considered as a natural result of learning;
- the student learns to read, speak, understand and write at the same time.

Business English in the learning process acts as a complex system consisting of [3]:

- from the language (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, syntax, etc.);
- content (marketing, management, finance, economics, etc.);
- communication skills (presentations, business correspondence, telephone conversations, etc.);
- intercultural communication.

We pay special attention to the organization of project work. The project method as a pedagogical technology includes a target orientation; scientific ideas on which the system of actions of the teacher and student is based; evaluation criteria and a qualitatively new product. The project method attracted the attention of Russian teachers already at the beginning of the 20th century. S.T. Shatsky, V. Petrova, N.K. Krupskaya, B.V. Ignatiev and others paid great attention to him [4].

A project involves a task that is presented to students for implementation, usually at the end of studying a particular topic. Its implementation gives students the feeling that a foreign language

– this is not the goal of teaching, but a means of communication. In the process of working on a project in class, a real activity situation is created. Following the authors of the design methodology V.Kh. Kilpatrick, J. Dewey and E. Dewey [5], we use the types of design work developed by them, filling them with new, necessary content for us based on the need to develop communicative competence [6]:

1. *Excursion Projects* are when students are sent to enterprises to find out how work is organized in one of the management processes, for example, marketing activities or advertising activities, followed by a presentation of the project in class. This type of project is actively used in the process of classroom work, as well as in preparing for the defense of bachelor’s and master’s degrees in English in the areas of training “Management”, “Human Resources Management”, “Vocational Training” (by industry).

2. *Hand Projects* – projects when bachelors and master’s students themselves make specific things, for example, drawings, embroidery or panels on the countries of the language being studied, which are later used to decorate foreign language classrooms.

3. *In game projects (Play Projects)*, bachelors and master’s students perform game roles. The university traditionally hosts Halloween, New Year, Christmas and others. No less interesting and useful for the professional development of future managers are the textbooks published at the university and constantly used in storytelling projects during professionally oriented role-playing and business games. These include such professionally oriented teaching aids as “Learning business English”, “Strategic management”, “Marketing” [3], which also received Informregister certificates and serve to develop professional competencies.

4. *Story Projects* are stories from students and undergraduates about various life events, singing songs in a foreign language, listening to stories from disks or tapes and then summarizing them. The Institute of International Management and Education widely uses textbooks by foreign authors in the “Market Leader” series (Publishing House “The Financial Times”), the textbook Nick Brieger and Jeremy Comfort “Early Business Contacts”, S. Graham “Jazz Chants” and “*Grammar Chants*” and others. Particularly popular are discs and cassettes with recordings of Christmas, New Year and Halloween songs, before studying and performing which students and undergraduates prepare project presentations of the history of holidays and songs.

The high efficiency of communicative teaching methods has been confirmed by practice. English has become one of the most interesting subjects for students. Annual monitoring of the quality of education carried out by the management of the institute within the framework of the quality management system shows that from 65 to 75% of first- and final-year students consider English the most interesting and necessary subject for their future work. Every year, the number of students entering the Institute of International Management and Education to receive education in the field of international management, logistics, personnel management, as well as in the field of foreign language – English – increases. The number of students who undergo practical training and internships abroad is growing, some of them are employed in international and foreign companies. Minor difficulties in adapting to the international educational and industrial environment are explained by the fact that the process of studying at the university gives students good knowledge of this environment:

- a number of subjects, such as regional studies, foreign economic activity, English for professional purposes, are taught in English;
- problems of foreign business and conditions of adaptation in the foreign labor market are studied independently and discussed at student research conferences in English;
- meetings and conversations are held annually with professors of foreign universities from Germany, Slovenia, China, Mongolia, the USA, etc.;
- interesting material for students is presented by bachelors and masters of foreign universities who come to the university through the AIESEC organization.

Thus, having analyzed the competencies necessary for the formation of students of non-linguistic faculties, we can identify the following of them, the development of which is aimed at building the process of foreign language education according to the developed model: foreign language communicative competencies (linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, sociocultural, social, strategic), professional competencies, general cultural competencies (instrumental, interpersonal, systemic).

As a result, the tasks that specify the goals of teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic faculties are formulated by us as follows:

1. Formation of appropriate competencies in all types of foreign language speech activities (reading, listening, speaking, writing), which represent the basis of linguistic competence.
2. Formation of general cultural competencies through knowledge about the culture of the country of the foreign language being studied and the development of skills and abilities to use the acquired ideas and knowledge in direct and indirect foreign language communication.
3. Formation of professional competence of students by means of a foreign language based on modeling professionally oriented learning content using the project method.

4. Formation of competencies (linguistic, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, discursive, strategic) that contribute to the implementation of foreign language professional (including business) communication through teaching foreign language professional discourse.

5. Formation of competencies that contribute to the development of the ability to independently engage in learning a foreign language.

6. Formation of a positive attitude (motivation) to learning a foreign language through the practical application of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

Let us consider the model we have developed for constructing the educational process of teaching a foreign language based on a competency-based approach for students of natural faculties. For a natural scientist conducting research, it is necessary to develop the skills of working with scientific information (articles, monographs, abstracts, etc.), as well as have the skills to present the results of scientific research, the ability to enter into controversy, and defend one’s opinion. Thus, we can identify qualitative characteristics that should be developed in professionally oriented foreign language education:

- the ability to adequately evaluate and extract the necessary information;
- the ability to argue and present the results of scientific activity;
- the ability to structure your statements logically and consistently;
- the ability to enter into contacts, maintain them or interrupt them;
- knowledge of ways and techniques of conducting discussions, discussing topics related to professional activities;
- the ability to listen to the interlocutor, to be tolerant of someone else’s point of view.

As a result, the implemented approach to the selection of training content corresponds to the principle of professionally oriented training, namely, creating in students the need to solve practical and professional problems by bringing the educational process as close as possible to activities related to their future profession. When choosing a training technology in the process of developing the above competencies, it is necessary to bring the educational process as close as possible to direct professional activity or its imitation. Such an approximation can be achieved by using appropriate forms of organization of the educational process in foreign language classes, which create optimal conditions for the interaction of participants in the study group, the manifestation of a personal position in relation to the problem under consideration, discussion and assessment of issues of a professional nature, which is typical for the realities of professional activity. We pay attention to the use of active group forms, namely:

- the method of developmental cooperation, which is characterized by the formulation of tasks that are difficult to complete individually, requiring the distribution of work in a group, the cooperation of students’ efforts;
- the project method as a set of educational and cognitive techniques that allow solving problems as a result of independent actions of students with the obligatory presentation of the results of the activity;
- a business game that helps to get closer to the situation of real communication, imitation of professional roles, etc.

CONCLUSION

Thus, a large scientific and educational work carried out by the Institute of International Management and Education of the university, aimed at developing communicative communication in the field of foreign language among students of the institute, is successfully carried out and

contributes to the integration of graduates of the institute into the international educational and industrial space, ensuring them the implementation of their goals life goals.

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